

Francesco Landini and the Italian Ars Nova:

Musical Philosophy and Innovations

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Francesco Landini (c. 1335–1397), one of the most celebrated Italian composers and organists of the 14th century, remains a figure shrouded in mystery, with much of his life and career obscured by misinformation and speculative accounts. Despite these uncertainties, Landini’s influence on the Italian Trecento and ars nova is undeniable. Renowned for his ballate, he advanced the genre through intricate melodies, ornamental style, and the distinctive “Landini Cadence,” which became emblematic of his music. His works, preserved prominently in the Squarcialupi Codex, display a remarkable blend of intellectual depth and artistic innovation rooted in his mastery of multiple instruments, philosophy, and poetry. Though many details of his life remain unclear, Landini’s legacy as a pioneering composer and virtuosic organist continues to captivate scholars and musicians alike, cementing his status as one of the most important figures in early Italian music.

Life and Career

Like many proclaimed “facts” of his life, the well-known idea of Francesco Landini’s family name has recently been deemed unaccepted by most scholars. Initially conceptualized was the notion that Francesco’s family name was Landini, from the painter Jacopo Landini. This has recently been surmised – according to Michael Scott Cuthbert, the name “Francesco da Firenze” is more suitable, as the surname “Landini”/“Landino” was not found in any sources linking to the composer during the 14th or 15th centuries. His presumed father has been identified as Jacopo del Casentino and noted as not having any connection to the Landini Family whatsoever.¹ Cuthbert fore mentions:

The only remaining evidence for the name “Landini” comes from the coat of arms, which appears above the head of the figure of the composer on his tomb (where he is also called Francesco). The stemma over his head, a pyramid of six mounds with three branches protruding from the top, matches a shield of the Landini family of Florence, one of four attributed to the family.²

Nonetheless, Landini was born c. 1335 in Fiesole, Italy, near Florence. As a child, he was blinded by smallpox. Early in life, he became devoted to many subjects, particularly music: he was a master of multiple instruments, including the organ, flute, rebec, lute – and many other instruments – and was also a singer. On top of this, of course, was his interest in writing poetry and composing – attributed especially to his wealth of knowledge in philosophy and astrology, wherein he was crowned the winner of a poetry contest in Venice in 1364 with a laurel wreath by the King of Cyprus.³

Landini wrote poetry in both Latin and Italian, although his poetry is more reputable due to his compositions set to them. It can be assumed that Landini spent time in northern Italy prior to 1370, which can mainly be attributed to a motet by a “Franciscus” dedicated to Adrea Contaraini, the Doge of Venice (1368-1382), along with his works being highly represented in sources from northern Italy. Early on in his life, he was given the job of organist for the Florentine monastery and the church of San Lorenzo, and he was also heavily involved in political and religious controversies.⁴ Approximately 1375, Andreas da Florentia, an associate of Landini’s at the Florentine monastery, hired him to help build the organ at the Florence Servite house, as well as the new organ at SS Annunziata in 1379 and at the Florence Cathedral in 1387. Lacking in information is documentation on Landini’s death, though it is known that he died on September 2nd, 139; however, the cause of death is not known. He was buried in Florence’s Church of San Lorenzo, where his tombstone is displayed, depicting him playing a portative organ.

Music and Influence

Landini’s musical style takes shape from the madrigal and the Italian Trecento style, often referred to as the “Italian ars nova.”⁵ Notably, his ballatas had a predominating top-part melody that was “vocal in character and highly ornamental.”⁶ His music was primarily secular, although

there are records of him composing sacred pieces; none of them have survived, however. Instead, a magnitude of ballate for two, three, and two and three voices are saved – Landini’s highly favored musical form – and a small number of madrigals. These pieces were recorded in the Squarcialupi Codex, where his compositions alone represent nearly a quarter of the surviving Tracento music.

Landini’s compositions were highly elaborate and used patterns, syncopated rhythms, and vocal runs. There was also a distinctive lack of emotional connection between the music and the words. Performances of his music included vocal performances, instrumental, or a mixture of both. Among these, over a hundred of his ballatas were monostrophic, which makes it questionable whether this structure was intentional or consequential.⁷ In his polyphonic ballatas, however, the music employs more dramatic tension. Rijk cites one of Landini’s compositions:

In Francesco Landini’s ballata “Abbonda di virtù chi senza vizio,” the ripresa presents the thesis, which asserts that anyone who serves Love in purity must be a person blessed with many virtues. [The] piedi and volta offer an explanation of the thesis, supported with arguments about the nature of Love. With the repetition of the ripresa, the thesis returns, consolidated and enhanced: anyone who serves Love in purity must be a person blessed with many virtues.

Much of Landini’s work includes strictly philosophical ballatas, which use tone to express the text of the poem. Among these are several ballatas based on love and other personal expressions. These highly reflect his interest in philosophy, and his combination of the poetic form with the music provides unification between the two subjects.⁸ His madrigals, on the other hand, consist of two musically contrasting sections, with the first section serving two to three three-line sections of the poem and the second half serving the concluding two lines of text. These compositions were usually composed for two or three vocalists, but just as with his ballatas, many were combined between voice and instrument on each melodic line.⁹

Landini also composed caccia, of which only two survive. These were hunting/fishing songs in a canon (or round) style with the poetic form of a madrigal. Other subjects for his music

include religion, love, convivial companionship, and historical events.¹⁰ Other compositional styles exist among Landini's work, however, including two tri-textual compositions written likely in imitation of the French motet, although "the texts may have been sung separately, one after another, two parts being played by instruments."¹¹ One of these pieces was also published in sonnet form, with the verse of the superius first, followed by the contratenor and tenor.

Another distinctive element of Landini's compositions is the "Landini Cadence," a common yet distinctive cadence during the Trecento wherein the leading tone drops to the sixth scale degree before resolving to the tonic note.¹² This cadence was not unique to his music or originated from him, and it can be found in numerous polyphonic pieces well into the 15th century. The earliest noted composer (at least in surviving works) who employed the cadence was Gherardello da Firenze – though it was also used by composers of the 15th century, including Gilles Binchois and Johannes Wreede. The name of cadence was appropriated as a result of Landini's consistent formulaic use of the passage throughout his compositions. The term was not coined until the 19th century, however, by German writer A.G. Ritter.¹³

Ecco la Primavera

Landini's duplum (including bass and tenor parts) ballata "Ecco la primavera" is a highly known composition of his, with Italian text and 3/4 meter that includes a simple structure, lyrical melody, and a lively dance step that follows a strict isorhythmic pattern. The composition includes a lot of thirds and sixths, aside from the perfect fifth and octave. Among these are typical characteristics of his writing, such as passing tones and neighbor tones to arrive at chromatically sharpened notes and a nearly identical rhythm in both parts to give it a distinctive homophonic texture. In most phrases, the two voices begin together, separate melodically, and return in unison. The poem also follows the structure of the ballata, as the form circles itself and ends with the same

refrain as its beginning. The text of the piece discusses the coming of spring, and the music's tone is set up to invoke an upbeat, dance-like piece that symbolizes happiness.¹⁴ The poem's text speaks of fresh grass, abundant flowers, and adorned trees before returning to the subject of love. Although written as a bass and tenor voice piece, many performances of the composition were done in an alto and soprano pair instead.

The Lesser Known

More uncommonly known about the composer includes his knowledge of science and its attribution to his compositions and writings. Historians have had great difficulty coming up with a sense of what writings Landini may have been exposed to, especially in his studies with great teachers and associates such as Antonio Pievano da Vado, an expert in Dante and teacher of logic.¹⁵

Rijk discusses Landini's philosophical attributions to his music:

[It] appears that Landini, with his renowned philosophical background, reinterpreted the fixed structure of the popular genre of the ballata as an excellent means to shape a logical demonstration. Of course, in reflecting upon Landini's way of shaping a philosophical concept in a musical composition, we cannot draw a direct parallel between a large treatise, such as the *Elements*, which clearly explicates the methods used and contains many components on which the procedure of demonstration is based ... and the short form of the ballata. But what we discern in Landini's text ... is the demonstration based on the axiomatic-deductive method, which successfully adopted the Euclidean model.

One criticism of Landini during his lifetime was by Anonymous V in his third volume of the *Cousse-maker Scriptorum*, who accuses Landini of "making improper use of red (actually white) notation. ... [The] unknown theorist quotes the music to the first phrase of the ballata, *Donna che d'amore*."¹⁶ Landini was not criticized much elsewhere, however. He was highly praised not only for his music, but especially for his virtuosic organ playing.

Giovanni da Prato wrote the *Romanza Il Paradiso degli Alberti* in 1389, a narrative that describes the Florentine life and daily activities using real characters, as a group living in the *Paradiso*. Landini also contributed to this, wherein he included his own stories or novella and

philosophical discussions by himself and various others. Ellinwood discusses Prato's notes of Landini's organ playing:

In one of the interludes of the third book ... Francesco plays his love verses so sweetly "that no one had ever heard such beautiful harmonies, and their hearts almost burst from their bosoms." On another occasion, when "a thousand birds were singing," Francesco was asked to play on his organ to see if their caroling would lessen or increase. [It] is reported, the singing became hushed as the birds listened to the musician, but then grew louder than ever, while a single nightingale flew down and perched on a limb above Francesco's head.

While Landini is known for his virtuosic works, the more difficult question is in the performance of his compositions. Theorists have conceptualized ideas that some of his compositions, generally ones with both melismatic and syllabic sections, were broken down into being both instrumental and vocal – melismatic runs at beginning and ending phrases were instrumental passages, with the syllabic sections being sung, also including the main portion of the verse. One other such theory concludes that these pieces of music were "primarily for organ, and that the voice could have sung nothing more than a simplified part, stripped of all ornamentation."¹⁷ Ellinwood notes that these theories lack clear, supportive evidence. However, there are several indications that work to oppose these ideas, more so than exist to support them.

Although much of what was previously known of Francesco Landini has been written off in recent times by scholars who have sought out more factual information about the composer, the truth in place still stands that Landini was a great poet and musician, revered as the "greatest Italian composer before the 16th century," whose work was highly influential on succeeding composers and those around him of his time. His musical abilities and compositional techniques are the works of a virtuoso, and while impressive during his lifetime, they continue to impress historians to this day.

Notes

1. Michael S. Cuthbert. "Tracento Fragments and Polyphony Beyond the Codex". Ph.D. Dissertation: Harvard University (Cambridge, MA, 2006): 492-43.
2. Ibid., 494
3. Anna Chiappinelli. *La dolce musica nova di Francesco Landini: una favola medievale*. Sidereus Nuncius, 2007.
4. Ibid.
5. Donald Jay Grout, *A History of Western Music*. New York, W.W. Norton & Company, 1960
6. "Landini, Francesco." Britannica Online Academic Edition, 2018, Encyclopædia Britannica, Inc.
7. Elena Abramov-van Rijk. "The Form of the Monostrophic Ballata as a Frame for a Logical Demonstration." *Plainsong & Medieval Music* 26, no. 1 (04, 2017): 1-18.
8. Ibid.
9. Grout, *A History of Western Music*.
10. Ibid.
11. Leonard Ellinwood. "Francesco Landini and His Music." *The Musical Quarterly* 22, no. 2 (1936): 190-216.
12. "Landini, Francesco." Britannica Online Academic Edition.
13. David Fallows. "Landini Cadence", *Grove Music Online*, ed. D. (2006).
14. Sirius L. Grammaticus. "Ecco La Primavera – Francesco Landini." March 03, 2018. <http://medieval-music.org/music/ecco-la-primavera-francesco-landini-remdih/>.
15. Rijk, "The Form of the Monostrophic Ballata as a Frame for a Logical Demonstration."
16. Ellinwood. "Francesco Landini and His Music."
17. Ibid.

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